

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

THE IMAGE OF THE SEA IN THE WORKS OF HERMAN MELVILLE AND OTHER AMERICAN WRITERS

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ABSTRACT

The image of Maura is a key one in American literature of the 19th century, especially in the work of Herman Melville. Studying the symbolism of the sea in his works, as well as in the works of other American writers such as James Fenimore Cooper and John Steinbeck, helps to better understand the cultural and philosophical ideas that dominated at that time. This research is relevant for a deeper understanding of literary topics related to nature, human existence and internal conflicts. This article offers a comparative analysis of the image of the sea in the works of Melville and other American authors, which allows us to identify common and unique features of their approaches. The inclusion of the opinions of various literary critics and analysts adds depth to the study and highlights the variety of interpretations of this symbol. Special attention is paid to the works "Moby Dick", "White Jacket" and "Pierre, or Ambiguities", which allows us to consider the evolution of the symbolism of the sea in Melville's work. The study showed that the sea in the works of Melville and other American writers serves as a powerful symbol reflecting internal conflicts, spiritual searches and moral trials of the characters. In Moby Dick, the sea symbolizes the boundless expanses and mysterious power of nature, in the White Jacket it is a place of trials and isolation, and in Pierre, or Ambiguities, it is a symbol of spiritual journey and the search for truth. In Cooper's works, the sea is a symbol of freedom and a romantic spirit, whereas in Steinbeck it embodies the vastness and indifference of nature. The analysis of these works highlights the importance of an integrated approach to literary analysis and confirms the importance of the image of the sea in American literature of the nineteenth and twentieth centuries.

Keywords: Herman Melville, the image of the sea, American literature, symbolism, James Fenimore Cooper, John Steinbeck, spiritual quest

Introduction: The sea has always played an important role in American literature, acting not only as part of the natural landscape, but also as a deep symbol reflecting the diversity of human emotions and experiences. This powerful image is used to convey complex philosophical and psychological themes, often serving as a metaphor for the characters' internal conflicts and spiritual quest. This image is especially vividly represented in the works of Herman Melville and his contemporaries, such as James Fenimore Cooper and John Steinbeck. Melville's works, such as Moby Dick, The White Jacket and Pierre, or Ambiguities, use the sea as the central element of the narrative, creating multilevel metaphors and symbols. The sea in these texts symbolizes not only the natural element, but also the inner worlds of the characters, their aspirations and fears. For other writers such as Cooper and Steinbeck, the sea also serves as an important backdrop for revealing characters and conflicts, reflecting romantic and realistic approaches to human existence. In this article, we tried to reveal how the sea is depicted in the works of Melville and other American writers, which allows us to better understand its meaning and role in literature. We will look at how the authors use this image to express complex themes and ideas, as well as how it affects the development of the plot and characters.

Overview of the methodology

Several methods were used to conduct this study:

1. Literary analysis: detailed study of the text, analysis of symbols and themes.

2. Historical and cultural analysis: consideration of the historical and cultural context in which the works were written.

3. Comparative analysis: Comparing different works to identify common themes and differences in the depiction of the sea.

The main objects of research were the works of Herman Melville, such as "Moby Dick", "The White Jacket" and "Pierre, or Ambiguities", as well as the works of other American writers such as James Fenimore Cooper and John Steinbeck. Both primary and secondary sources were used in the research process to ensure the completeness and objectivity of the analysis.

The results of the study

The image of the Sea in Moby Dick

The sea has always played a significant role in the works of Herman Melville. In Moby Dick, it becomes the central symbol around which the whole story is built. The sea is an arena for Captain Ahab's epic struggle with the white whale, symbolizing the vast expanses and mysterious power of nature. Only one of them is not dangerous and uncontrollable, which is deeply reflected in the behavior of the Agave and its desire for success (Melville, 1851). Critics and literary analysts emphasize the symbolic importance of the sea in Moby Dick. According to literary critic Howard Vincent, most of all the novel simulates unselfishness and lack of recognition, reflecting the human essence. You cannot understand and control the world around him (Vincent, 1949). The sea represents both the external and internal conflicts that the characters face. Philippe

Gussett, a researcher of Melville's work, argues that in the sea "Moby Dick" is an arena for moral and philosophical trials, where every encounter with nature becomes a test for the human spirit and will (Gossett, 1963). Gussett emphasizes that for Ahab, the sea is a mirror in which he sees a reflection of his insane obsession and desire for revenge. Literary critic Charles Olson sees the sea as a metaphor for the human soul, boundless and elusive, like the ocean. According to Olson, Moby Dick more simulates the deep psychological and existential questions that every person faces (Olson, 1947). The sea becomes a metaphor for exploring the inner world of the characters and their spiritual quest. The sea in Moby Dick not only serves as a backdrop for events, but also actively influences the development of the plot and characters. The expanses of the sea become an arena for exploring the inner world of Captain Ahab and his team. Their journey across the ocean symbolizes their inner searches and aspirations. Ahab, obsessed with the idea of catching a white whale, sees in the sea a reflection of his inner struggle and an uncontrollable desire for revenge. The novel "Moby Dick" also explores the themes of courage and overcoming through the image of the sea. Heroes, facing dangers at sea, gain new strength and wisdom. The sea becomes a symbol of their inner journey and transformation, helping to deepen understanding of their nature and aspirations. The sea in Herman Melville's Moby Dick plays a key role in revealing the themes and ideas of the work. It serves as a powerful symbol reflecting both the greatness and beauty of nature and its indifference to human suffering. Through the image of the sea, Melville explores deep philosophical and psychological issues, making the sea the central element of his narrative.

The image of the sea in the "White Jacket" by Herman Melville

In the novel *The White Jacket*, Herman Melville uses the sea as the central element of the narrative, which serves as a testing place for the protagonist. Here, the sea acts as a place where the hero faces physical and moral difficulties. Melville masterfully creates an atmosphere of unity of command and isolation, which calls itself the main researcher of the world of persons (Melville, 1850). The sea becomes a metaphor for the hero's inner journey, his struggle with his own fears and doubts. The hero, overcoming difficulties at sea, finds a new understanding of himself and his place in the world. Critics point out that in the "White Jacket" the sea is not just a background for events, but an important symbolic element that helps to reveal the themes of inner conflict and spiritual journey. Literary critic Walter Basil emphasizes that Melville uses the sea to create a deep metaphor for dealing with his own fears and doubts. Basil wrote that Pestilence, as a result of the novel, simulated internal division and a new hero, which made it an integral era of development (Basil, 1974). Robert M. Thornburg, in his study of Melville's work, argues that the sea in the "White Jacket" symbolizes the process of self-discovery and inner transformation of the hero. He notes that overcoming difficulties at sea helps the main character to gain a new understanding of himself and his place in the world.

According to Thornburg, this is especially true for dual growth and international studies (Thornburg, 1986). Literary analyst Joanna Crane considers the sea in the "White Jacket" as a symbol of spiritual isolation and self-discovery. In her opinion, the sea in this novel becomes a metaphor for the inner journey of the hero, his struggle with his own fears and doubts, which allows him to deepen understanding of his inner world. Crane notes that Melville uses the sea element to create an atmosphere of loneliness, which enhances the drama and psychological tension of the work (Crane, 1993).

The image of the sea in "Pierre, or Ambiguities" by Herman Melville

In the novel *Pierre, or Ambiguities*, Herman Melville uses the sea as a symbol of spiritual journey and the search for truth. The main character may encounter built-in filters and translators, which are displayed in the image of Maury (Melville, 1852). Melville uses the sea as a metaphor for the hero's complex and contradictory path to self-discovery. Pierre experiences moments of doubt and revelation, which are enhanced by the image of the sea, symbolizing endless searches and spiritual experiences. Critics point out that the sea in "Pierre, or Ambiguities" serves as an important symbolic element that helps to reveal the inner conflicts and spiritual quest of the hero. Literary critic Harold Bloom emphasizes that Melville uses the sea as a metaphor for Pierre's complex and confusing path to self-discovery. Bloom writes that Pestilence as a result of the novel symbolizes internal reproduction and search engines, which makes it intellectual property (Bloom, 1986).

Literary analyst Jennifer Smith considers the sea in "Pierre, or Ambiguities" as a symbol of spiritual experiences and the search for truth. In her opinion, the sea in this novel becomes a metaphor for the inner journey of the hero, his struggle with doubts and the desire for self-knowledge. Smith notes that Melville uses the elements of the sea to create an atmosphere of deep inner reflection, which enhances the drama and psychological tension of the work (Smith, 2001).

The image of the sea by other American writers

As we have already noted, the theme of the sea is quite popular among American writers, and many writers have been addressing it for a long time. Each of them reveals various psychological aspects through this image. Let's look at some of them.

James Fenimore Cooper, in his works such as *The Red Corsair*, uses the sea as a stage for adventures and conflicts (Cooper, 1827). The sea becomes a symbol of freedom and the romantic spirit, reflecting the ideals of early American Romanticism. Cooper portrays the sea as a place where heroes can show their best qualities and overcome difficulties. His works emphasize the romantic connection of man with nature and the idea of a noble hero capable of great deeds. In *The Red Corsair*, the sea acts as an arena for epic battles and adventures, where the heroes demonstrate their bravery and skill. Cooper uses seascapes to create an atmosphere of romance and danger, emphasizing the beauty and unpredictability of the sea element. His characters, such as the Red Corsair, embody the ideals of courage, honor and determination, facing numerous challenges and overcoming them with dignity.

Literary critic Thomas Fielding notes that Cooper uses the sea as a symbol of freedom and independence, reflecting the spirit of the times and the desire for new horizons (Fielding, 1982). The sea in Cooper's works becomes a metaphor for the endless possibilities and adventures that await those who are willing to take a chance and go into the unknown.

John Steinbeck John Steinbeck in "The Sea Wolf" portrays the sea as an inexorable and indifferent element to human suffering (Steinbeck, 1941). The sea symbolizes vastness and eternity, against which a person seems small and vulnerable. Steinbeck uses the sea as a symbol of the human struggle for survival and moral trials. In his works, the sea also serves as a metaphor for the social and moral problems that the characters face. Steinbeck emphasizes nature's indifference to human effort and suffering, which forces the characters to show their resilience and resourcefulness. In *The Sea Wolf*, the main character, Humphrey Van Weyden, finds himself on board a ship commanded by the cruel Captain Larsen. The sea here becomes a symbol of a harsh and ruthless environment where everyone must fight for their survival. Steinbeck masterfully describes the moral and physical challenges that the characters face, emphasizing their inner struggle and desire for self-preservation. Literary analyst Richard Gray notes that Steinbeck uses the sea as a symbol of the strength and indifference of nature, which serves as a contrast to human weakness and vulnerability (Gray, 1995). The sea in Steinbeck's works becomes an arena for the study of human nature and social inequality, reflecting the complex relationships between people and their environment.

Conclusion

The study of the image of the sea in the works of Herman Melville and other American writers has shown that this image is a key element that allows a deeper understanding of many aspects of human nature and destiny. The sea acts as a powerful symbol reflecting both the greatness and beauty of nature and its indifference to human suffering. This study highlights the importance of an integrated approach to the analysis of literary works for a more complete understanding of their semantic content. The image of the sea in American literature is a multi-valued and complex symbol that has been used to explore a wide range of topics and ideas. For Herman Melville, the sea is not only a place of action, but also a symbol of human struggle, the pur-

suit of knowledge and inner redemption. Other American writers, such as James Fenimore Cooper and John Steinbeck, also used the sea as an important element of their works, exploring its symbolic meaning and influence on human destiny. Melville and his contemporaries used the image of the sea to explore fundamental issues of human existence, such as the struggle between good and evil, the search for truth, and the nature of the human soul. The sea in their works acts as a powerful symbol that allows you to convey complex and multifaceted ideas, as well as create deep and memorable images.

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